

METHODS FOR DETERMINING THE DUST AND MOISTURE CAPTURE EFFICIENCY OF AIR PURIFIERS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines modern experimental methods for determining the level of dust concentration and moisture content in the air. During the study, the potential of using gravimetric and photo colorimetric methods to assess the dust and moisture retention efficiency of air purifiers was analyzed. To determine dust concentration, analytical aerosol filters AFA-V-18 were employed, and the mass concentration of particles in the airflow, as well as the permeability indicators of the filters, were evaluated. The photo colorimetric method and the gravimetric measurement of retained moisture were used to determine the effectiveness of moisture retention. The findings of this research contribute to determining the operational efficiency of air purification devices, assessing their dust and moisture protection properties, and expanding the possibilities for their application in practical conditions.

Determining the dust capture efficiency of air purifiers.

During dust testing, the gravimetric efficiency of air purifiers is evaluated by weighing the dust deposits on aerosol filters. The moisture content is then determined using either a photocolometric method or a gravimetric method of measuring the retained moisture.

As these methods differ from one another, we will consider them separately.

The dust level of the purified air stream within the pipe is measured using AFA-V-18 filters, which are installed in an allonge connected to the suction pipe.

The AFA-V-18 analytical aerosol filter, made from a synthetic nonwoven material, is highly efficient, enabling it to capture almost all particles regardless of their size. The AFA-V-18 filter also features a high flow rate (100 L/min) combined with low aerodynamic resistance (1.5 mm water column).

The filter consists of its main part and a cassette, which serves to hermetically seal the filter in the allonge. For an AFA-V-18 filter with a self-weight of 100 mg, dust accumulation from 1 mg to 100 mg is permitted.

Before the experiment, the filter was kept at room temperature for 30-60 minutes and then weighed. After the samples were collected, the filter was again kept under the initial conditions for 30-60 minutes and then weighed on an analytical balance. The air sampling time t for the filters is limited by the maximum permissible amount of dust and is determined by the following formula:

$$t = \frac{60a}{qQ}, \text{ min,} \quad (1)$$

Where q is the estimated or permissible limit concentration of dust, mg/m^3 ; a is the maximum permissible amount of the dust sample, mg ; Q is the air flow rate through the suction pipe, m^3/h .

The airflow rate Q passing through the aerosol filters is determined according to the calibration graphs of the diaphragms in the air sampling line.

The post-filter dust concentration is calculated using the following formula:

$$q_2 = \frac{(g_2 + g_1)}{Qt_2} 60, \quad (2)$$

Where q_2 is the mass concentration of dust particles, mg/m^3 ; g_1 is the weight of the clean filter, mg ; g_2 is the weight of the dust-filled filter, mg ; Q is the air flow rate through the filter, m^3/h ; t_2 is the sampling duration, min .

The pre-filter dust concentration is determined using the following formula:

$$q_2 = \frac{60G}{(Q_x + Q_0)t_1} \text{ mg / m}^3, \quad (3)$$

Where G is the amount of dust supplied through the dispenser during the experiment, mg ; Q_x is the flow rate of purified air that has passed through the air purifier, m^3/h ; Q_0 is the volume of air suctioned from the air purifier, m^3/h ; t_1 is the experiment duration, min .

The transmission coefficient of the air cleaner is determined by the following expression:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{q_2}{q_1} = \frac{g_2 - g_1}{G} \frac{Q_x + Q_0}{Q}, \quad (4)$$

The cleaning coefficient, or efficiency, of an air purifier is determined as follows:

$$\eta = (1 - \varepsilon) 100\%, \quad (5)$$

When using the absolute filter

$$\varepsilon = \left(1 - \frac{g_0}{G}\right) \frac{Q_x + Q_0}{Q_x} 100\%, \quad (6)$$

Where g_0 is the weight gain of the absolute filter installed in the air stream drawn from the air purifier, gm ; G is the amount of dust collected during the experiment, g .

To determine the size of the dust particles, the AFA-V-18 aerosol filter is weighed and then installed on a special frame, which is placed over a beaker containing acetone.

Acetone vapors dissolve the filter, transforming it into a transparent film. Dust particles trapped by the filter become embedded within this film, making it suitable for microscopic analysis. The moisture retention efficiency was determined using the photo colorimetric method. This involved accounting for the moisture captured by the air purifier (a method similar to the absolute filter method).

In the first method, water dyed with brilliant green is supplied to the air purifier via a dispenser. Moisture droplets exiting the air purifier along with the air are deposited on the AFA-V-10 analytical aerosol filter, staining it with the dye.

Air samples were taken from the downstream flow of the air purifier according to the method described above. However, the difference was that a flow-directing device, equipped

with an allonge holding an AFA-V-10 filter, was attached to the end of the air intake tube.

At the end of the experiment, the stained filter is removed from the allonge, dried, and dissolved in acetone. The concentration of the dye solution is determined using a FEK-56 photo electro colorimeter. This instrument is designed to measure the optical density or light transmittance of liquid solutions by both the absolute method, i.e., relative to the solvent, and the relative method, i.e., relative to a standard solution. To determine the concentration of the solutions, the instrument is first calibrated using a set of standard solutions.

When determining solution concentrations, the effect of the dissolved filter on the instrument readings is taken into account. The correction is made using a calibration graph that shows the change in the light transmittance of acetone as a function of the weight of the filter dissolved in it.

The moisture retention capacity of the air purifier is determined by the following formula:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{g(Q_x + Q_0)}{G_x c Q}, \quad (7)$$

Where g is the amount of dye, in grams (g), deposited on the aerosol filter and dissolved in acetone, determined using a photocolorimeter based on the concentration of the colored analytical filter; $Q_x + Q_0$ is the total airflow through the air purifier, in m^3 ; G_s is the amount of water, in grams (g), poured into the air purifier during the experiment; c is the initial concentration of the dye in the water, in g/cm^3 ; and Q is the airflow rate through the sampling tube, in m^3 , determined according to the calibration graph for the diaphragms in the sampling system.

Using the second method, the efficiency of the air purifier was determined as follows. The moisture captured by the air purifier drained into the box where the filter was installed and collected there. After the experiment concluded, this moisture was poured into a measuring container. A correction for evaporation and moisture loss, as determined experimentally, was then applied to the measured amount of moisture.

In this case, the efficiency of the air purifier will be as follows:

$$\eta = \frac{g_n}{G_n}, \quad (8)$$

Where g_n is the amount of retained moisture, taking into account carry-over and evaporation, in g; G_n is the amount of moisture supplied during the experiment, determined by the dispenser's calibration graph, in g.

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